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THE EVOLUTION OF THE ENGLISH NOVEL: FROM DEFOE TO DICKENS

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Abstract: *This article serves to reveal the development of English novels more widely. It highlights the main aspects of novels in the era of Defoe and Dickens.*

Key words: *creativity ,novels,essay, social context, influential writer.*

The English novel as we know it today has undergone a significant development from the early 18th century to the Victorian era. Starting from the realism and satirical adventures of writers such as Daniel Defoe, the novel expanded to the complex human emotions, social commentary and artistic creativity that can be seen in the works of Charles Dickens. This essay explores how the English novel evolved from Defoe to Dickens and explores the changes in narrative style, thematic focus, and broader social context that have influenced these two influential writers.

The Beginning: Daniel Defoe and the Early English novel: It is often said that the modern English novel began with Daniel Defoe (1660-1731), whose seminal work *Robinson Crusoe* (1719) is considered one of the first true novels of English literature. Defoe's style was revolutionary for its time, as it moved away from the allegorical or romantic narrative traditions that had dominated the past centuries. Instead, Defoe wrote in a realistic style, focusing on detailed descriptions of daily life, personal survival and adventures.

In *Robinson Crusoe*, Defoe explores themes of isolation, self-reliance and human ingenuity, telling the story of a man stranded on a deserted island for 28 years. What sets Defoe apart from previous writers is his commitment to realism. His characters are not knights, gods or mythical figures; they are ordinary people who find themselves in unusual situations. With his first-person narration and quasi-historical tone, Defoe invites readers to immerse themselves in a believable world. His work also explores the rise of individualism and colonialism. Another significant work of Defoe,

Moll Flanders (1722), develops the narrative of the novel, focusing on the life of the main character, which is morally ambiguous.

In this short story, Defoe explores the complexities of crime, poverty and survival in a growing capitalist society. The novel "The Trials of the Shopping Center" examines the attitude of the public to morality, class and gender, which expands the thematic scope of the novel as a form. Defoe's works laid down many elements that later defined the English novel: an emphasis on realism, the development of the personal path of a main character and the study of individual consciousness in a social context.

The growth of social and psychological depth: innovations of the 18th century According to Defoe, Samuel Richardson (1689-1761) and Henry Fielding (1707-1754) made significant contributions to the development of the novel in the XVIII century. Richardson's novels Pamela (1740) and Clarissa (1748) are early examples of an epistolary novel in which the story is told through letters. This form allowed for greater psychological depth, as it revealed the innermost thoughts and feelings of the characters in real time. Richardson was particularly interested in issues of morality, virtue and gender relations - topics that would run through the entire history of the novel. Fielding, on the other hand, took a different approach. His most famous work, Tom Jones (1749), is a rogue novel full of humor, irony and broad social overtones. Unlike Richardson, Fielding embraced the chaos of the human experience, presenting a more comical and sometimes cynical view of society. With an omniscient narrator, Fielding introduced a degree of narrative control and commentary that enriched the structure of the novel. The works of Defoe, Richardson and Fielding laid the foundation for the further development of the novel into a form that could explore not only external adventures, but also internal psychological struggles, while commenting on the complexity of society. Jane Austen and her focus on family life At the beginning of the 19th century, Jane Austen (1775-1817) had reinterpreted the English novel and shifted his focus to domestic life and social relations, especially in the context of marriage and family. In novels such as Pride and Prejudice (1813) and Common Sense and Sensitivity (1811), Austen used wit, irony and sharp social observation to examine the restrictions imposed on women by patriarchal society. Austen's novels differ from those of Defoe and Fielding in that they focus on dialogue and the subtleties of social interaction. Their characters are not adventurers or scammers; they are men and women who understand the complexities of love, duty and decency.

However, behind these family problems lies a sharp criticism of class inequality, gender roles and personal autonomy.

Austen brought a new level of psychological realism to the English novel, especially in the depiction of the inner life of women. She was deeply engaged in the emotional and intellectual development of her characters, which set the stage for more subtle and socially conscious novels of the Victorian era.

The Victorian Novel: Charles Dickens and Social Realism: With the advent of Charles Dickens (1812-1870), the English novel reached new heights in popularity, range and social impact. Dickens is perhaps a typical writer of the Victorian era, and his works reflect the complexities and contradictions of Victorian society. Unlike Austen, who focused on the nobility and middle class, Dickens explored the lives of the poor, the working class and the marginalized. In novels such as *Oliver Twist* (1837-1839) and *David Copperfield* (1849-1850), Dickens described the grim reality of life in industrial Britain: child labor, poverty and the inhuman effects of urbanization. His characters often embody social types — the stingy Scrooge, the innocent orphan, the corrupt bureaucrat - but they are portrayed with such vivacity and humanity that they go beyond a simple caricature. One of Dickens's most significant contributions to the development of the novel was his ability to combine social criticism with a fascinating narrative. His novels, published in weekly or monthly serial editions, were enthusiastically received by a wide readership, which made him one of the first "celebrity" authors. Dickens used his platform to advocate for social reform, especially in his later works such as *Bleak House* (1852-1853) and *Hard Times* (1854), which expose the moral shortcomings of the British legal and industrial system. Another key element of Dickens' novels is his masterful use of language and narrative techniques. Using vivid descriptions, irony, satire and melodrama, he created fascinating worlds in which readers could easily get lost. Although his characters are often exaggerated, they are found among readers due to their universal emotional struggle. The development of the theme from Defoe to Dickens. The theme of the novel has expanded significantly from Defoe to Dickens. While Defoe was mainly concerned with personal survival and adventure, Dickens used the novel as a platform to explore broader social issues. Dickens' works are notable for their focus on the social structure of Victorian Britain — the inequality between rich and poor, the corruption of institutions, and the need for empathy and reform. Both Defoe and Dickens were realists in their own way, but where Defoe focused on individual victories over adversity, Dickens focused on the collective struggle of society. Dickens's novels are full of unforgettable characters, whose personal stories reflect the larger social problems of the time, and his ability to evoke both humor and pathos made his works resonate with readers of different classes. From the early realism of Daniel Defoe to the socially oriented works of Charles Dickens, the English novel has undergone significant changes. From an emerging narrative

focused on the adventures of individuals, it has become a sophisticated means of social criticism and psychological research.

Conclusion

Drawing on the innovations of Defoe, Richardson, Fielding and Austen, Dickens brought the novel to its Victorian heyday, making it a central component of popular and literary culture. The novel has become not only entertainment, but also a powerful tool for solving urgent problems — inequality, poverty and the human condition. As the novel developed, it remained a reflection of the times, constantly adapting to the changing social, economic and cultural conditions of Great Britain and beyond.

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